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Research Article

Role Of Clinical Pharmacist In The Assessment Of Risk Factors For Tuberculosis Incidence And Management- A Prospective Interventional Case Control Study

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ABSTRACT

Back ground of the study: Tuberculosis, better known as TB, is a lung disease caused by a bacterium called Mycobacterium Tuberculosis. Tuberculosis is a bacterial infection spread through inhaling tiny droplets from the coughs or sneezes of an infected person Initial empiric treatment of TB starts patient on a 4-drug regimen; Isoniazid, Rifampin, Pyrazinamide, Ethambutol or streptomycin after 2 months of therapy Pyrazinamide can be stopped then Isoniazid + rifampin can be continued as daily or intermittent therapy for 4 more months.

Objectives: To evaluate the role of clinical pharmacist in the management of Tuberculosis including improvement in Medication Adherence and improvement in Quality of life. Identify the risk factors such as Smoking, Alcohol, BMI, HIV, Diabetes Mellitus, Age, Gender, and Residence for the prevalence of Tuberculosis.

Study design: A Prospective Interventional Case control study was conducted from December 2017-May 2018 at a 350-bedded Tertiary care teaching hospital in South India.

Methodology: The study includes 200 tuberculosis diagnosed patients. In which 100 were included in case group and remaining were included in a control group to which only Anti-Tubercular therapy was given without

performing any patient counselling and patient education. In Case group patient counselling and patient education was provided along with Anti-Tubercular therapy.

Results: A total 200 tuberculosis diagnosed patients were included in the study. out of 200 patients Age group: 48 patients in the age group between 66 – 75 years with (24.0%). Gender -125 patients with (62.5%) were found to be male and 75 patients with (37.5%) were found to be female. Smoking -123 patients with (61.5%) were found to be due to smoking and 77 patients with (38.5%) were non-smokers. Diabetic- 95 patients with (47.5%) were diabetic patients and remaining 105 with (52.5%) patients were non-diabetics. HIV- 69 patients with [34.5%] were found to be suffering from Tuberculosis due to HIV infection and 131 patients with (65.5%) were found to be HIV-ve patients. Alcoholic- 109 patients with [54.5%] were found to be suffering from Tuberculosis due to excessive alcohol intake and 91 patients with (45.5%) were non-alcoholics. Residence- 139 patients with (69.5%) were found to be suffering from Tuberculosis are rural people and 61 patients were urban residents. BMI- 101 patients were found to be suffering with Tuberculosis due to malnutrition with BMI < 18.5. knowledge about disease, patient medication adherence, quality of life was improved.

Conclusion: clinical pharmacist plays an important role in evaluating the risk factors for tuberculosis, patients in case group have shown improvement in knowledge about disease, patient medication adherence, and quality of life by providing effective patient counselling.

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INTRODUCTION:

Tuberculosis is a type of lung infection which is caused by Mycobacterium Tuberculosis. Infection can occur from one person to other person by inhaling the tiny droplets from infected person or through air . Various types of Tuberculosis are Latent tuberculosis, pulmonary tuberculosis and extra pulmonary tuberculosis. The risk factors includes- Age progression, Intake of excessive alcohol, smoking, malnutrition, health care workers, contact with active tuberculosis patients. Signs and symptoms include chronic cough, haemoptysis, fever, night sweat, fatigue, weight loss, decreased appetite, several tests are performed to diagnose tuberculosis like mantoux test, chest x- ray, sputum smear microscopy, culture test, genexpert test. Treatment for tuberculosis includes: Directly Observed Treatment Short Course and Revised National Tuberculosis Control Program.

First line drugs are Isoniazid, Pyrazinamide, Ethambutol, Rifampicin and second line drugs are streptomycin, Amikacin, Capreomycin, and Neomycin. Recklessness, lack of knowledge, distance, and cost of medication, symptomatic relief, and unavailability of drug is the reason for patient non-compliance. The role of clinical pharmacist plays an important role in providing the importance of drug therapy in the treatment of Tuberculosis

Role of clinical pharmacist:

Clinical pharmacist plays an important role in tertiary care hospital. Clinical pharmacists have well knowledge in pharmacotherapy as well share their knowledge to other health care professional in interdisciplinary hospital

Clinical pharmacist needs to explain to the patients about the importance of medication adherence and Problems associated with non-medication adherence. Clinical Pharmacist plays an important role in educating the patients about the disease and symptoms and provides continuous patient monitoring and patient counselling thereby improving the patient's quality of life.

AIM:

The purpose of the study is to identify the risk factors that are responsible for prevalence of Tuberculosis and to evaluate the role of clinical pharmacist in improving

Patient Knowledge, Medication Adherence and Overall quality of life of TB diagnosed patients.

OBJECTIVES:

- Identify the risk factors such as smoking, alcohol and other factors for the prevalence of Tuberculosis.
- To evaluate the role of clinical pharmacist in the management of Tuberculosis including improvement in Medication Adherence and improvement in Quality of life.
- Understanding the reasons for patients non-medication adherence and improve the patients medication adherence through effective patients counselling and patient education.
- Reduce the recurrence of Tuberculosis.
- To improve overall quality of life of patients.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Study Site: The study was conducted at MNR General Hospital, Fasalwadi, Sangareddy, Telangana.

Study Period: The study was carried out for a period of six months from December 2017- May 2018.

Study Design: A Prospective Interventional Case control Study.

Study population – The study population include 200 in patients and data was collected in the data collection form and written consent form was taken from all the patients. IEC letter was obtained from the hospital before conducting the study.

Study Criteria:**Inclusion criteria:**

- Patients of either sex diagnosed with pulmonary tuberculosis
- Patients with sputum positive and smear positive
- Patients willing to participate in the study.

Exclusion Criteria:

- Patients of age > 80 years
- Patients not willing to participate in the study.

METHODOLOGY:

The study include 200 tuberculosis diagnosed patients. In which 100 were included in case group and remaining were included in a control group to which only Anti-Tubercular therapy was given without performing any patient counselling and patient education. In Case group patient counselling and patient education was provided along with Anti-Tubercular therapy.

Ethical considerations:

Letter of ethical clearance was obtained from the ethical review board. Privacy and confidentiality was ensured during the pharmaceutical care services.

Obtaining clearance certificate from institutional ethical committee

For obtaining the ethical clearance certificate and application along with study protocol which include the proposed title, study site, inclusion and exclusion criteria, objective and methodology about the work to be carried out was submitted to chairman of the institutional ethical committee of MNR hospital.

RESULTS:

Table 1: Age Wise Distribution of Cases

S.No	Age In Years	No of patients	Percentage (%)
1.	25 – 35	23	11.5 %
2.	36 – 45	25	12.5 %
3.	46 – 55	41	20.5 %
4.	56 – 65	63	31.5%
5.	66 – 75	48	24.0 %

Out of 200 patients, 23 patients were found in the age group between 25 – 35 years with (11.5%) followed by 25 patients in the age group between 36 – 45 years with (12.5%), 41 patients were found in the age group between 46 - 55 years with (20.5%), 63 patients were found in the age group between 56 – 65 years with (31.5%), followed by 48 patients in the age group

STATISTICAL INTERPRETATION:**Analysis of data**

The data of the selected patients were collected from pulmonology department, according to inclusion and exclusion criteria and were evaluated prospectively for the presence and fulfilment of the following parameters.

Name, Age, Gender, I.P No, Lab investigations, Chief complaints, Diagnosis, Drug chart/treatment plan, Patient questionnaire/ Medication history interview form, Patient education leaflet.

The data was analysed by using PRISM software. After that the data was reviewed and evaluated. The data was summarized and described by using descriptive statistics by physician's acceptance. Mean standard deviations were done for patients of age, smoking, alcohol and other factors are assessed for its significance using Chi-square (χ^2) test.

between 66 – 75 years with (24.0%). The age group which is at higher risk of Tuberculosis is 56 – 65 years with (31.5%) as in older people immune system undergoes gradual weakening with age.

Figure 1: Age wise distribution of cases

Table 2: Gender Wise Distribution of Cases

Gender	No of Patients	Percentage (%)
Male	125	62.5%
Female	75	37.5%

Out of 200 patients diagnosed with Tuberculosis, 125 patients with (62.5%) were found to be male and 75

patients with (37.5%) were found to be female. Male patients are at higher risk of Tuberculosis.

Figure 2: Gender wise distribution of cases

Table 3: Smokers v/s Non-Smokers

Parameter	No of Patients	Percentage (%)
Smokers	123	61.5%
Non-Smokers	77	38.5%

Out of 200 patients diagnosed with tuberculosis, 123 patients with (61.5%) were found to be due to smoking and 77 patients with (38.5%) were non-smokers. Smoking plays an important role in the prevalence of

Tuberculosis. Smoking could decrease the immune response and damage the function of cilia in the airways which increases the risk of Tuberculosis.

Figure3: Smokers v/s Non-Smokers

Table 4: Diabetics v/s Non-Diabetic cases

Parameter	No of cases	Percentage (%)
Diabetic cases	95	47.5%
Non-Diabetic cases	105	52.5%

Out of 200 patients diagnosed with tuberculosis, 95 patients with (47.5%) were diabetic patients and remaining 105 with (52.5%) patients were non-diabetics. diabetes depresses or let down the immune

response, which in turn facilitates infection with mycobacterium, Tuberculosis and progression to symptomatic disease.

Figure 4: Diabetics v/s Non - Diabetic cases

Table 5: HIV +ve Cases v/s HIV -veCases

Parameter	No of cases	Percentage
HIV + ve	69	34.5%
HIV - ve	131	65.5%

Out of 200 patients diagnosed with tuberculosis, 69 patients with [34.5%] were found to be suffering from Tuberculosis due to HIV infection and 131 patients with (65.5%) were found to be HIV - ve patients. HIV

is considered as a strong risk factor for Tuberculosis as it weakens the immune system and increases the risk of Tuberculosis.

Figure 5: HIV + ve Cases v/s HIV - ve Cases.

Table 6: Alcoholic v/s Non-Alcoholic patients

Parameters	No of cases	Percentage
Alcoholic Cases	109	54.5 %
Non-Alcoholic cases	91	45.5 %

Out of 200 patients diagnosed with tuberculosis 109 patients with [54.5%] were found to be suffering from Tuberculosis due to excessive alcohol intake and 91 patients with (45.5%) were non-alcoholics, more than 40 gms of ethanol per day resulted nearly three-fold

increase in the risk of Tuberculosis. Alcohol consumption was estimated to be responsible for approximately 10% of all incident cases and deaths due to Tuberculosis Alcohol is a modifiable risk factor and avoiding alcohol will reduce the TB severity.

Figure 6: Alcoholic v/s Non-Alcoholic patients

Table 7:Urban Area v/s Rural Area

Residence	No of cases	Percentage
Urban area	61	30.5 %
Rural area	139	69.5 %

Out of 200 patients diagnosed with Tuberculosis 139 patients with (69.5%) were found to be suffering from Tuberculosis are rural people and 61 patients were

urban residents. Rural people are at increased risk of developing Tuberculosis infection due to lack of knowledge, unhygienic condition etc.

Figure 7: Urban area v/s rural area

Table 8: BMI v/s No of Cases

Parameter	No of Cases	Percentage (%)
BMI < 18.5	101	50.5 %
BMI > 18.5	99	49.5 %

Out of 200 patients diagnosed with Tuberculosis 101 patients were found to be suffering with Tuberculosis

due to malnutrition with BMI < 18.5 due to lack of proper nutrition.

Figure 8: BMI v/s No of Cases

Table No: 9 Knowledge About Disease:

S.No	Patients having knowledge			Patients with lack of knowledge		
	Days	Case group	Control group	Days	Case group	Control group
1.	10	37	41	10	63	59
2.	50	77	45	50	23	55

Out of 200 patients, 100 patients were taken under case group and remaining 100 were considered under the control group. In case group along with anti – Tubercular therapy, patient counselling and education regarding the disease was provided whereas the control group were on anti – Tubercular therapy without patient counselling. In case group at the 10th day of admission 37 patients had little knowledge about disease which is increased up to 63, where as in control group without patient counselling 41 patients had knowledge about disease which has increased to 59. So due to effective patient counselling by clinical

pharmacist at the end of 50th day only 23 people out of 100 were unaware about disease in case group and almost 55 patients from control group were still lack of knowledge without effective patient counselling. Chi-square test has been performed. (χ^2) value for patients having knowledge is 4.772 and (χ^2) for patients with lack of knowledge is 9.526 at 10th and 50th day of counselling with degrees of freedom 1, P value is 0.021 so $P < 0.05$ hence there is a statistically significant difference between before and after counselling in case and control group.

Figure 9: Knowledge about disease

Figure 10: Patients With Lack Of Knowledge

Table 10: Patient medication adherence

S. No	Medication adherence			Non-medication adherence		
	Days	Case group	Control group	Days	Case group	Control group
1.	10	33	49	10	67	51
2.	50	87	41	50	13	59

Out of 200 patients diagnosed with Tuberculosis, 100 patients were taken under case group and remaining 100 under control group. At the 10th day of admission in case group only 33 patients were found to adhere with medication which is increased up to 67 with effective patient counselling where as in control group the number has increased from 49 to 51 without patient counselling. so at the end of 50th day in case group only 13 patients were found to be non – adherent to their medication with effective patient counselling,

where as in control group 59 patients were still non-adherent to medication without patient counselling. Chi-square test has been performed. (χ^2) value for patients with medication adherence is 8.537 and (χ^2) for patients with non-medication adherence is 17.23 at 10th and 50th day of counselling with degrees of freedom 1, P value is 0.035 so $P < 0.05$ hence there is a statistically significant difference between before and after counselling in case and control group.

Figure 10:

Table 11- Overall quality of life

S. No	Quality of life improved			Quality of life worsened		
	Days	Case group	Control group	Days	Case group	Control group
1.	10	37	42	10	63	58
2.	50	75	49	50	25	51

Out of 200 patients 100 were considered under case group and remaining 100 patients under control group.

In case group along with Anti – Tubercular therapy effective patient counselling was provided which

increased the overall quality of life of a patient. At the 10th day of admission out of 100 patients in case group 37 patients had good quality of life which is increased to 63 with effective counselling and education where as in control group it has increased from 42 to 58 due to lack of counselling and at the end of 50th day only 25 patients from case group had worsened quality of life and almost 51 patients from control group were

noticed.. Chi-square test has been performed. (χ^2) value for patients with improved quality of life is 4.331 and (χ^2) for patients with worsened quality of life is 7.548 at 10th and 50th day of counselling with degrees of freedom 1, P value is 0.0060 so $P < 0.05$ hence there is a statistically significant difference between before and after counselling in case and control group.

Figure 11:

Statistical Analysis:

parameter	Test performed	Value	Degree of freedom	P-value	Result
Patients having knowledge	Chi-square test	4.772	1	0.02	significant
Patients with lack of knowledge	Chi-square test	9.526	1	0.0020	significant
Medication adherence	Chi-square test	8.537	1	0.0035	significant
Non-medication adherence	Chi-square test	17.23	1	0.0001	significant
Quality of life improved	Chi-square test	4.331	1	0.0374	significant
Quality of life worsened	Chi-square test	7.548	1	0.0060	significant

Statistical analysis:

Statistical interpretation was done by using Prism graph pad software and mean and standard deviation were derived by using Chi- square test.

DISCUSSION

Age: In relation to the parameter 1, Out of 200 patients the age group which is at higher risk of developing Tuberculosis 56-65 years with a percentage of (31.5%) because age factor plays a major role in the Tuberculosis treatment and is in accordance with the work done by Joel Negin et al; who concluded that almost 50 % of the patients in their study were older people aged >45 years

Gender: Male / female: In relation to the parameter 2, Out of 200 patients, 125 patients are male and 75 patients are female Which is in support of the work done by Umakanth M et al; who concluded that out of 105 patients, 67 patients were male and 38 patients

were female in their study. Nearly 80% patients are male.

Smoking: In relation to the parameter 3, Out of 200 patients 123 patients were found to be smokers with (61.5%). The non- smokers are 77 patients (38.5%) which is in support of the work done by Shrishail S Patil et al;who concluded that the percentage of smokers is (71.6%) and non-smokers is (28.3%) in their study similar to our results. Smoking increases the risk of TB.

Alcohol Consumption: In relation to parameter 4, Out of 200 patients 109(54 %) patients were found to be alcoholics and non- alcoholics were found to be 91 patients with(45.5 %)which is in support of the work done by karthickeyan Duraisamiet al. who concluded that the percentage of alcoholics is (68.57%) and Non-alcoholic patients is (31.43%) in their study.

BMI: In relation to parameter 5, Out of 200 patients 101 patients [50.5%] were found to be suffering from

lack of proper nutrition (malnutrition).which is in support of the work done by Colleen F. Hanrahan et al.; who concluded in his study that out of 100 patients 54 patients are found to be normal and 39 patients are under weight and remaining 7 patients were obese in their study and has concluded that malnutrition was one of the important modifiable risk factor for Tuberculosis incidence.

Diabetes Mellitus: In relation to parameter 6, Out of 200 patients suffering from Tuberculosis,95 patients [47.5%] were diabetics which is in support to the work done by Ali Nasir Siddiqui et al; who concluded that out of 103 patients 22 patients were found to be diabetic patient in their study and has concluded that diabetes mellitus was one of the important risk factor for the prevalence of Tuberculosis.

HIV Infection: In relation to the parameter 7, Out of 200 patients 69 patients [34.5%] were found to be suffering with HIV infection which is in support of the work done by soham gupta et al.; who concluded from their study that (8.9 %) were HIV +ve and (59.4 %) are HIV –ve and concluded that HIV is an important risk factor for Tuberculosis prevalence.

Residence: In relation to the parameter 8, Urban / rural area: Out of 200 patients in our study 61 patients are from urban area and 139 patients are from rural area with the percentage of 67.5% which is in support with the work done by Muhammed Umair Mushtaq et al; who concluded from their study that the chance of Tuberculosis infection in rural areas is almost double than the urban area.

In Relation with Knowledge:

Case Group - On the 10th day of admission 37% of patients in case group are having knowledge of tuberculosis and 63% of patients are lack of knowledge. On 50th day after the continuous monitoring and patient counselling knowledge about the disease in the case group has increased significantly to 77%.

Control Group - On the 10th day of admission 41% of patients in case group are having knowledge of tuberculosis and 59% of patients are lack of knowledge. Without patient counselling and knowledge about the disease in the control group there is no such significant improvement to 45% .

This is in support of the work done by Gail M Kele et al., who concluded that out of 350 Tuberculosis patients 309 patients were aware of disease at the end due to effective patient counselling provided by clinical pharmacist.

In Relation with Medication Adherence:

Case Group - On the 10th day of admission 67% of patients in case group were exhibited non medication adherence and 33% of patients exhibited medication adherence. On 50th day after the continuous monitoring and patient counselling and patient education there was a significant improvement (87%).

Control Group - On the 10th day of admission 49% of patients in control group are having knowledge of tuberculosis and 51% of patients are lack of knowledge. Without patient counselling and knowledge about the disease in the control group there is no such significant improvement to 41%

This is in support of the work done by Shaip krasniqiet al., who concluded that out of 350 Tuberculosis patients 288 patients were adhere to medication by providing proper and effective patient counselling.

In Relation with Over All Quality Of Life:

Case Group -On the 10th day of admission 37% of cases were found to be exhibited improved quality of life and 63% of cases were found to be with poor quality of life. After 50th day of admission 72% of cases were found to be exhibited for Improved quality of life.

Control Group – On the 10th day of admission 43% of cases were found to be exhibited improved quality of life and 57% of cases were found to be with worsening quality of life. After 50th day of admission only 49% of cases were found to be exhibited for Improved quality of life which is significantly low because improvement of quality of life is very much essential for any patient who takes medication continuously .the quality of life of tuberculosis patients depends on medication adherence and positive attitude towards disease this can be achieved by affective role of clinical pharmacist by providing patient counselling and patient education.

This is in support of the work done by Madeeha Malik et al., who concluded that out of 350 Tuberculosis patients 311 patients had experienced good quality of

life after providing effective patient counselling by clinical pharmacist.

CONCLUSION

From the above study it was concluded that patients of extreme of Age, Male patients, Malnourished, Smokers, Alcoholics, Diabetes Mellitus, HIV infection, Residence are more prone to Tuberculosis infection.

Clinical pharmacist plays an important role in improving the knowledge about the disease. Knowledge about the disease ultimately increases the knowledge of the patients about severity and causative factors for Tuberculosis and importance of following strict medication adherence.

Continuous medication adherence is very much essential for the patients who were diagnosed with Tuberculosis as it takes at least 6 months of continuous medication usage to get complete cure of tuberculosis, which can be achieved and improved by continuous patient counseling, patient education and patient monitoring by the clinical pharmacists.

Improvement of quality of life can be seen in those patients who have taken medications continuously. The quality of life of Tuberculosis patient depends on medication adherence and positive attitude towards the disease. This can be achieved by effective role of clinical pharmacist by providing patient counseling and patient education.

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